

SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPROVING THE TEACHING METHODOLOGY OF EFFICIENT COTTONSEED DELINTING TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation: This article examines the laboratory methodology for effectively teaching the process of cottonseed processing using local linter equipment in higher education institutions. It highlights the organization of practical training sessions, algorithms for conducting experiments, analysis of measurement results, and methods for developing students' competencies.

Keywords: Fiber, lint, equipment, working chamber, resource-saving, cottonseed, technology, linter, energy.

Introduction. Globally, cotton fiber is the primary raw material for the textile industry, while cotton lint (linters) serves as a key raw material for the chemical and pulp-and-paper industries. Ensuring the high-quality production of fiber and lint products requires special attention to the implementation of modern, resource-efficient equipment and technologies in production processes. In countries with developed cotton industries, as well as in our republic, extensive scientific research is being conducted on improving cotton processing technologies. In particular, efforts are focused on increasing the productivity of linters used in cottonseed delinting, reducing the number of linters in technological processes, saving electrical energy and spare parts, maintaining environmental standards within industrial facilities, and improving the quality of processed cottonseed and lint. These studies aim at developing and introducing scientifically grounded, modern equipment and technologies into production.

Main part and results. At cotton ginning plants, the seeds obtained after the ginning technological process are cleaned of impurities and then directed to delinting equipment. A portion of the foreign materials present in seed cotton passes through the ginning process and contaminates the seeds. The seeds exiting the gin may contain large particles such as sand, plant debris, accidentally introduced metal fragments, small stones, as well as defective (immature or hollow) seeds. When transported through screw conveyors and elevators, these materials can be crushed, increasing the contamination level of the processed lint. If ginned seeds are properly cleaned, the resulting lint becomes less contaminated, the linter saws are not damaged, and their service life is extended. Therefore, seeds are cleaned of impurities before being fed into delinting equipment.

Currently, a pneumatic seed cleaner of the USM type is used to remove impurities from seeds. Compared to other models, the USM pneumatic cleaner has a compact design and is simple and convenient to operate. Its operation is as follows: seeds are fed by the collecting conveyor of the linter line and, through a paddle drum, enter the separation chamber via an opening in the suction pipe. As the airflow lifts the seeds upward, heavier particles fall to the bottom of the shaft and are separated. The cleaned, healthy seeds are then directed through

barriers and a vacuum valve and transported by a screw conveyor to the required location (linter equipment). [2]

The main function of linters installed in the delinting departments of cotton processing enterprises is to mechanically remove lint from the surface of cottonseed using saw teeth. The following requirements are imposed on linters: during the delinting process, neither the seed nor the lint should be damaged; impurities must not mix with the lint; and mechanisms must be in place to regulate lint quality, the fuzziness level of the seed, and the productivity of the linter. In the delinting technological process, mechanical action is applied to the seeds, and the feeding process operates in a semi-automatic manner, belonging to straight-flow mechanisms.

The separation of lint from saw teeth is carried out with the help of an air chamber, through which the lint is transported upward into the air duct. Depending on the number of saws, linters are commonly referred to as 160-saw linters. Since the seed roll cannot rotate freely under the influence of the saws during the delinting process, a rotating agitator (moving in the opposite direction to the saw) is installed in the linter chamber to facilitate its rotation. This agitator not only rotates the seed roll but also loosens it, improving the contact of fuzzier seeds with the saw teeth.

The principle of lint separation in linters is based on the mechanical action of rotating saws on the seed roll to scrape lint from the seed surface, followed by separating the lint from the saw teeth using airflow and transporting it to a condenser, where it is separated from the air. The main performance indicators of a linter are the amount of lint removed from the seeds and its productivity in terms of seed processing.[3]

Figure 1. Scheme of the 5LP Linter

- 1 – feed roller;
- 2 – leveling and cleaning drum;
- 3 – profiled working chamber;
- 4 – agitator (mixer);
- 5 – grate (grid bars);
- 6 – saw cylinder;
- 7 – air chamber;
- 8 – waste screw conveyor;

To ensure complete and high-quality lint removal, both the agitator and the seed comb play important roles. The main function of the agitator is to direct the seeds within the working chamber toward the saw teeth. The function of the seed comb is to prevent the passage of seeds that still retain an excessive amount of lint.

The removed lint passes through the gaps between the grate bars together with the saw teeth and is then separated from the saw teeth by airflow. The separated lint is cleaned and sent to the pressing section. Depending on their design, linters allow the use of saws with diameters of 320, 310, 300, and 288 mm. When installing saws of different diameters, it is necessary to readjust the position of the air chamber and the grate grid. The gap between the saw teeth and the nozzle of the air chamber is adjusted by shifting the chamber horizontally using special screws [4].

In recent years, efforts have been made to improve linters, increase their productivity, raise the number of saws on the saw shaft, enlarge the working chamber volume, and study their effects on the quality and quantity of lint and seeds. Based on these studies, optimal speed modes for the saw cylinder and agitator have been developed. It has been found that seeds rotating under the influence of agitators and saw teeth with different linear speeds are periodically affected by the teeth of the saw cylinder.

The saw teeth primarily affect the seeds at three points:

Near the seed comb, at the entrance to the working chamber, where the seeds come into contact with the saw teeth, change their direction of movement, and begin moving in the direction of the teeth. At this stage, due to low density, lint is partially removed from the seed surface;

When the seeds pass between the agitator and the saw teeth, they are in a compact state, and the main portion of lint is removed;

When the saw passes through the spaces between the grate bars.

Conclusion and recommendations. The working chamber of the machine has a significant impact on the delinting process. In modern 5LP linter machines, the linear speed of the saws on the saw cylinder is 12.3 m/s, while the linear speed of the agitator blades is 4.2 m/s. Based on this, it can be assumed that the saw teeth act on the seed mass at a speed of 8.1 m/s.

At such high speeds, the impact of the saw on the seeds, as well as the ضرب (impact) of the agitator on the seed roll, can cause damage to the seeds during the process of scraping lint from their surface. If the density of the seed roll is low, the agitator blades cannot exert sufficient pressure on the seeds. In this case, the efficiency of lint removal decreases, and at the same time, the likelihood of seed damage increases due to excessive mechanical воздействия.

References:

1. Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021 in five priority areas. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947, dated February 7, 2017.
2. I.D. Madumarov, M.A. Gapparova, T.O. Tuychiev. Methodological Guide on the Primary Processing of Natural Fibers. Tashkent, 2013. P.Ш. Сулаймонов, Б.Я. Кушакеев, Д.У. Мадрахимов. Изыскание путей повышения эффективности процесса линтерования семян. Отчет АО «Пахтасаноат илмий маркази». Ташкент. 2011.-65 с
3. P.Ш. Сулаймонов. Совершенствование базовых звеньев пильного линтера и его освоение в производстве. Отчет ОА «Пахтасаноат илмий маркази». Ташкент. 2016. – 51 с
4. Т.М. Кулиев, P.Ш. Сулаймонов и др. Пахтани дастлабки ишлаш бўйича қўлланма. Тошкент- "Afvto-nashr". 2019. -477 б
5. Сулаймонов P.Ш., Маруфханов Б.Х., Каримов У.Қ. Аррали линтернинг ишчи қисмларини такомиллаштириш ва ишлаб чиқаришга тадбиқ этиш. Илмий ҳисобот. "Пахтасаноат илмий маркази" АЖ. Тошкент. 2016.- 51 б